

Acetoacetarylarnides as Chelating Ligands: Part IV. Iron(III) Chelates*

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In earlier papers, extensive investigations on the chelating behaviour of acetoacetarylarnides towards transition metals namely, VO^{+2} (IV), Co(II) , Ni(II) , Cu(II) , UO_2^{+2} (VI) and MoO_2^{+2} (VI) have been reported¹⁻⁵. Recently Sen *et al*⁶. have reported the preparation of chromium (III) and titanium(IV) complexes of these ligands. This communication describes the synthesis and characterisation of iron (III) chelates with acetoacetanilide, acetoacet-*o*-chloroanilide and acetoacet-*o*-anisidide. Korkuc and Lipiec⁷ have reported a spectrophotometric solution study of the ferric acetoacetanilide system and observed a 1 : 1 composition of the complex having instability constant value, $k=4 \times 10^{-3}$.

EXPERIMENTAL

Acetoacetanilide (Ace-anil), acetoacet-*o*-chloroanilide (Ace-Cl-anil) and acetoacet-*o*-anisidide (Ace-anis) were B.D.H. (England) L.R. variety and used directly. Other chemicals used were all of G.R.E. Merck variety.

Tris (acetoacetanilido) Iron(III) Monohydrate (Dark red): Ferric chloride hexahydrate (1 mole) was dissolved in minimum amount of water and few drops of conc. HCl. Acetoacetanilide (2 mole) was dissolved in minimum amount of hot water. These two solutions were then mixed and to the resulting violet solution aqueous sodium acetate was added drop by drop with stirring. The dark red crystals formed were suction filtered, washed with water and dried in a desiccator over CaCl_2 . Found: Fe, 9.5; N, 7.1; H_2O (by loss at 110°), 2.5%, Λ_M in methanol = 4 mhos $\text{cm}^2 \text{mole}^{-1}$, $\mu_{\text{eff.}} = 5.82$ B.M. at 300°K . $[\text{Fe(Ace-anil)}_3]$. H_2O requires Fe, 9.3; N, 6.9; H_2O , 2.9%.

*Tris (acetoacet-*o*-chloroanilido) Iron(III)* (Dark red) was prepared by following a similar procedure as for the above compound except that acetoacet-*o*-chloroanilide was dissolved in minimum amount of alcohol. A red oil separated was scratched with water to get the crystals. These were filtered off, washed repeatedly with water and then with aqueous alcohol and dried as usual. Found: Fe, 8.3; N, 6.3%, Λ_M in methanol = 4 mhos $\text{cm}^2 \text{mole}^{-1}$, $\mu_{\text{eff.}} = 5.85$ B.M. at 300°K , $[\text{Fe(Ace-Cl-anil)}_3]$ requires Fe, 8.1; N, 6.1%.

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Tris(acetoacet-o-anisidido) Iron(III) (Dark red) was prepared by adopting a similar procedure as for the acetoacet-o-chloroanilido compound. Found: Fe, 8.5; N, 6.3%. Λ_M in methanol = 5 mhos $\text{cm}^2 \text{mole}^{-1}$, $\mu_{\text{eff.}} = 5.90$ B.M. at 302°K. $[\text{Fe}(\text{Ace-anis})_3]$ requires Fe, 8.3; N, 6.2%.

The complexes are in general soluble in methanol, ethanol and insoluble in water. The complexes do not decompose even on heating at 120° for hours.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

When ferric chloride is added to an aqueous or alcoholic solution of the reagent, a fine violet colour is formed. This violet colour is specific for acetoacetarylamides and no other metals interfere. The minimum amount of iron detected was found to be 2.30 γ/ml . Acetoacet-o-toluidide also forms this characteristic colour, but isolation of solid complex has appeared unsuccessful. The electrolytic conductance measurements in G.R. methanol indicate non-electrolytic nature of the complexes. The 10cm temperature magnetic moment ($\mu_{\text{eff.}} = 5.8-5.9$ B.M.) of the complexes are close to the spin only value, which indicates that the ground state has no angular momentum precluding the possibility of orbital contributions to the magnetic moment. The electronic absorption spectra of the complexes in ethanol indicate that the complexes are transparent in the 330-800 $\text{m}\mu$ region. Only a charge transfer type of band was noticed in these complexes (viz. at 400 $\text{m}\mu$ $\epsilon = 1.6 \times 10^4$ litre $\text{mole}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$). This observation is in line with other O_h symmetry spin free iron (III) complexes⁸. The stronger ΔE values in trivalent iron is reflected in exhibiting charge-transfer bands in the near ultraviolet which have sufficiently strong low energy tails in the visible to obscure almost completely the very weak, spin-forbidden ligand field bands.

The formula of the complexes, $[\text{Fe}(\text{AA})_3]$ (where AA = a molecule of acetoacetarylamide), their paramagnetism and electronic absorption spectra indicate that the complexes have an octahedral structure.

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